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Research Article

Phytochemicals Enriched Herbal Oral Care Formulations for Enhanced Dental Health

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ABSTRACT

Salvadora persica (miswak) is a traditional medicinal plant widely used for oral hygiene. The roots of Salvadora persica possess strong antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, making them suitable for use in herbal oral care formulations. The aim of this study was to formulate and evaluate Salvadora persica root extract-based oral care products to improve dental hygiene and prevent common oral diseases. Roots of Salvadora persica were collected from Trikaripur, Kasaragod, and subjected to successive solvent extraction. Pharmacognostic and phytochemical evaluations were carried out to ensure the quality and presence of bioactive constituents. Antimicrobial activity of the extract was assessed against Lactobacillus using the agar well diffusion method, and the results were compared with an amoxicillin disc as the standard control. Antioxidant activity was evaluated using the DPPH free radical scavenging assay. Based on the results, herbal gel toothpaste, herbal chewable oral care tablets, and herbal tooth powder were formulated using the root extract. The prepared formulations were evaluated for quality, stability, and efficacy. The findings demonstrated satisfactory antimicrobial and antioxidant activities, confirming the effectiveness of the formulations. The study concludes that Salvadora persica is a promising natural ingredient for oral care products and provides a safe herbal alternative for maintaining oral hygiene and preventing dental disorders.

INTRODUCTION

HERBAL FORMULATIONS

Herbal formulations are dosage forms prepared from one or more herbs or processed herbal

substances in specified quantities to provide therapeutic, nutritional, or cosmetic benefits. These formulations are widely used to diagnose, prevent, and treat diseases, as well as to maintain overall health. They are prepared using various processes such as extraction, distillation,

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purification, and fermentation, and may include whole plants or their parts in fresh or dried forms. Herbal medicines are gaining increasing attention due to their natural origin, cost-effectiveness, and relatively fewer side effects compared to synthetic drugs. However, they also present certain limitations such as variability in composition, slower onset of action, and lack of standardization.

Advantages:

- Herbal medicine can be used to treat wide range of ailments.
- The cost of herbal medicines are very low compared to pharmaceutical drugs.
- Herbal medicine are obtained naturally and only involve lesser chemical process for their formulation hence it is considered as eco friendly.
- Extracts of plant decreases the bulk property of cosmetics and gives appropriate pharmacological effects.
- Easily available & found in large variety & quantity.

Disadvantages:

- Herbal drugs have slower effects as compare to allopathic dosage form.
- They are difficult to hide taste and odour.
- Most of the herbal drugs are not easily available.
- Manufacturing process are time consuming and complicated.
- No pharmacopoeia defines any specific procedure or ingredients to be used in any of herbal cosmetics.

HERBAL COSMETICS

Herbal cosmetics are the product, which are formulated by using various herbal ingredients to form the base that are used to provide defined cosmetic benefits. Due to its purity, safety and efficacy herbal cosmetics are popular around the world. Herbal cosmetics are formulated using various herbal extracts containing a wide range of active principles such as glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids, carotenoids, terpenoids, saponins, vitamins, amino acids, sugars, essential oil, enzyme etc.

HERBAL GEL TOOTHPASTE

Herbal gel toothpaste is a modern oral care formulation designed to promote dental health using plant-based ingredients. It typically contains natural extracts such as *Salvadora persica* (miswak), along with gelling agents and mild abrasives, providing gentle cleansing, antimicrobial action, and plaque control. Compared to conventional toothpaste, herbal gel formulations offer a safer and more eco-friendly alternative with minimal use of synthetic chemicals.

Advantages:

- Contains natural ingredients with fewer harsh chemicals.
- Provides gentle oral-cleansing action suitable for regular use.
- May help reduce the growth of plaque-causing oral bacteria.
- Supports oral hygiene and helps freshens breath naturally.

- Contains antioxidant compounds that may help protect oral tissues from oxidative damage.

HERBAL CHEWABLE ORAL CARE TABLET

Herbal chewable oral care tablets are solid dosage forms designed to dissolve upon chewing. They releasing herbal extracts and bioactive compounds that help reduce oral bacteria, control odor, and maintain oral hygiene. Their pre-measured dosage ensures convenience, improved compliance, and suitability for individuals with swallowing difficulties. Additionally, they are portable, eco-friendly, and reduce plastic waste compared to conventional oral-care products.

Advantages:

- Improved patient compliance.
- Enhanced patient adherence.
- Suitable for patients with swallowing difficulties.
- Accurate, unit-dose delivery.
- Environmentally sustainable, Extended shelf stability, Enhanced portability.

HERBAL TOOTH POWDER

Herbal tooth powder is a natural oral hygiene formulation made from finely powdered herbs and minerals. It provides mechanical cleaning along with antimicrobial and antioxidant benefits. Ingredients such as *Salvadora persica* (miswak) help control plaque, reduce oral bacteria, and freshen breath. Due to their chemical-free composition, sustainability, and effectiveness, herbal tooth powders are increasingly popular as an alternative to conventional toothpaste.

Advantages:

- Natural and chemical-free.
- May help reduce growth of certain oral bacteria. Supports oral hygiene.
- Freshens breath naturally.
- Eco-friendly and sustainable.
- Typically has a long shelf life if stored properly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

PLANT COLLECTION

The fresh root of *Salvadora persica*, were collected from Trikaripur, Kasaragod district, Kerala (India) in the month of October 2025. The herbarium was prepared by drying the specimens in the shade and then labeling them with the relevant information.

PLANT AUTHENTICATION

The plant material was identified and authenticated by Dr. Subrahmanya Prasad.K, Assistant professor, Department of botany, Nehru Arts and Science College, Kanhangad, Padannakkad.

PLANT PROFILE

Salvadora persica

Synonyms

Arak, Sewak, Peelu, Toothbrush tree

Scientific classification of *Salvadora persica*

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta
Super division	Spermatophyta
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	Rosidae
Order	Brassicales
Family	Salvadoraceae
Genus	Salvadora
Species	<i>Salvadora persica</i>

Morphological characteristics

Salvadora persica is a small to medium sized tree, typically growing up to 3-6 meters tall. The root of *Salvadora persica* is a thick, deeply penetrating taproot with many spreading lateral roots. The outer part of the root is fibrous and light brown, while the inner part is soft and white, which is the portion used as miswak. The root is highly adapted to salinity and drought conditions. It contains antimicrobial compounds, silica, and fluoride, giving it medicinal properties. The stem is straight, with a smooth, grayish brown bark that peels off in thin layers. The branches are spreading, with a rounded crown. The leaves are elliptical or ovate, with a pointed tip, typically 2-5 cm long and 1-2 cm wide, and they are arranged oppositely on the stem. It produces small, greenish yellow flowers and are arranged in axillary clusters. The fruit is small, red or purple and are typically 1-2 cm in diameter.

Phytochemical constituents

- Alkaloids: Salvadorine and Trimethylamine.
- Sulfur Compounds: Benzyl isothiocyanate and Elemental sulfur.
- Flavonoids: Kaempferol, Quercetin, and Rutin.

- Glycosides: Salvadoside, and Salvadoraside.
- Sterols: β -sitosterol, and Stigmasterol.
- Vitamins and Minerals: Fluoride, Calcium, Phosphorus, and Vitamin C
- Silica and Saponins.
- Essential oils / Terpenoids

Medicinal uses

Antibacterial, Antioxidant, Astringent, Oral hygiene (Natural toothbrush), gastrointestinal benefits, antidiabetics effect etc.

PREPARATION OF PLANT EXTRACT

Extraction of *Salvadora persica* was carried out by maceration. Maceration is an extraction technique used to extract bioactive compounds from plant material.

Procedure:

- The extract was prepared by maceration process.
- The collected plant materials were washed, air dried and coarsely powdered.
- Maceration: 10g of coarsely powdered *Salvadora persica* was soaked in conical flask containing 100 ml of distilled water (10% w/v).
- Seal the conical flask and keep it in a dark place with occasional shaking to facilitate extraction.
- Finally, the sample extract was filtered through Whatman NO:1 filter paper, Collect the extract and store in a desiccator for further studies.

PHARMACOGNOSTIC STUDY

A. Determination of moisture content

B. Determination of ash value

- Total ash
- Acid insoluble ash
- Water soluble ash

C. Determination of Extractive value

- Alcohol soluble extractive value
- Water soluble extractive value

PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING

The extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to detect the various phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, glycosides, carbohydrates, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and phenols.

INVITRO-ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

Antibacterial activity was determined by agar well diffusion method, activity of extract was tested against *Lactobacillus*.

Procedure:

Preparation of pre-inoculum: The bacteria *Lactobacillus* is prepared from curd. The curd is filtered and the broth is incubated at 25°C for 24 hours.

Preparation of pour plates: A sabouraud dextrose agar (150 ml) is autoclaved and poured to the already autoclaved plate and cooled to room temperature and allowed to solidify. The culture was spread on the agar surface aseptically by using sterilized cotton.

Making wells on agar plates: Wells of 6mm in diameter were made aseptically on the agar plate by using a sterilized well digger. The extract is aseptically added in to the well by using a micropipette. The petri plates are kept in a refrigerator (1hr) for the diffusion of substances from well in to surrounding medium. During this time the growth of the organism is reduced: After 1 hour, the plates were incubated in inverted condition at 37°C for 48 hours.

Measurement of the zone of inhibition: After 48 hours, the plates were observed for the presence of inhibition of bacterial growth, and it was indicated in the form of a clear zone of inhibition around each well containing the extract. The size of the inhibitory zone was measured in 'mm'. The zone of inhibition obtained for the developed herbal extract was compared with the standard. Amoxicillin disc was used as standard.

ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

- The free radical scavenging capacity of extracts were determined using DPPH. DPPH solution was prepared in 90% methanol.
- Extract (*Salvadora persica*) was mixed with 95% ethanol to prepare the stock solution (5µg/ml).
- 150 ml of freshly prepared DPPH solution was taken in test tubes and 75 ml of varying concentration of extract was added to every test tube and the final volume was made to 3ml with methanol.
- After 10 min, the absorbance was measured at 517 nm using a spectrophotometer.
- Ascorbic acid was used as reference standard and dissolved in methanol to make the stock solution with the same concentration (5µg/ml).

- Control sample was prepared containing the same volume without any extract and reference (ascorbic acid).
 - 95% methanol was used as blank.
 - % scavenging of the free radical was measured using the following equation,
- $$\%RSA = \frac{\text{Abs control} - \text{Abs sample}}{\text{Abs control}} \times 100$$

Where,

RSA= Radical Scavenging Activity.

Abs control= absorbance of DPPH radical + methanol.

Abs sample= absorbance of DPPH radical + extract.

FORMULATION OF HERBAL GEL TOOTHPASTE

SR. NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1	<i>Salvadora persica</i> extract	3g	2.5g	2.5g
2	Carbopol 940	1g	1g	1g
3	Triethanolamine	q.s	q.s	q.s
4	Propylene glycol	4ml	5ml	3.5ml
5	Glycerin	8ml	8ml	7.5ml
6	Hydrated silica	4.5g	5g	5g
7	Methyl paraben	0.15g	0.15g	0.15g
8	Propyl paraben	0.12g	0.12g	0.12g
9	Sodium saccharin	0.3g	0.3g	0.3g
10	Peppermint oil	0.5ml	0.5ml	0.5ml
11	Distilled water	Up to 100ml	Up to 100ml	Up to 100ml

Procedure:

- Carbopol 940 was dispersed in distilled water and allowed to hydrate for 1 hour.

- Triethanolamine was added dropwise under continuous stirring to adjust pH (6.5–7.5) and form gel base.
- Glycerin and propylene glycol were added and mixed thoroughly to obtain a uniform gel base.
- Methyl paraben and propyl paraben were dissolved in propylene glycol and incorporated with continuous stirring.
- Hydrated silica was added as an abrasive agent and mixed uniformly.
- Sodium saccharin was added as a sweetening agent.
- Peppermint oil was added for flavoring.
- *Salvadora persica* extract was incorporated and triturated to ensure uniform dispersion.
- The final volume was made up to 100 mL with distilled water and stirred until a homogeneous gel toothpaste was obtained.

EVALUATION OF HERBAL GEL TOOTHPASTE

F1, F2, F3 was prepared and subjected to following evaluation method.

1. Physical Evaluation:

The colour, state, and appearance of the gel toothpaste were examined visually.

2. pH test:

Take 1gm of the herbal gel toothpaste in a 150ml beaker and add 10ml Of freshly boiled and cooled water. Stir well to form a uniform suspension, and determine the pH of the suspension using pH meter.

3. Spreadability test:

Approximately 1–2 g of herbal gel toothpaste was placed between two glass slides (10 × 10 cm). A known weight was applied, and the slides were moved in opposite directions. After 3 minutes, the spread length was measured. The test was performed in triplicate, and spreadability (S) was calculated using the formula:

$$S = (M \times L) / T$$

Where,

M is the applied weight, L is the length of spread, and T is the time required to separate the slides.

4. Extrudability:

The formulation was filled into collapsible aluminum tubes, sealed, and weighed. Tubes were placed between glass slides, clamped, and subjected to a 500 g load. The cap was removed, and the extruded paste was collected and weighed. Extrudability was expressed as the percentage of paste extruded.

5. Abrasiveness:

Approximately 15–20 cm of toothpaste was extruded from each of ten tubes onto butter paper. Samples were visually inspected and gently spread to detect the presence of coarse or sharp particles.

6. Fragrance Test:

A small quantity of each formulation was placed on a clean watch glass and evaluated organoleptically for odor type and intensity.

7. Shape retention:

The herbal gel toothpaste was dispensed onto a toothbrush and allowed to stand for 10 seconds. The shape retention was evaluated and graded as:

(A) shape maintained, (B) shape mostly maintained, or (C) shape not maintained.

FORMULATION OF HERBAL CHEWABLE ORAL CARE TABLET

SR. NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1	<i>Salvadora persica</i> extract	2.5g	2.5g	2.5g
2	Mannitol	13g	15g	15g
3	Sodium bicarbonate	1.5g	1.5g	2g
4	Acacia	2.5g	2g	3g
5	Magnesium stearate	0.3g	0.2g	0.3g
6	Talc	0.2g	0.2g	0.3g
7	Menthol	0.1ml	0.1ml	0.1ml

Procedure:

- Weigh all the powdered ingredients Mannitol, Sodium bicarbonate, Acacia, Magnesium stearate, Talc required for the formulation.
- Mix all the powdered ingredients in the mortar and pestle. Triturate them for size reduction and uniform mixing.
- Then add menthol and weighed herbal ingredient like *Salvadora persica* extract to the above mixture again blended well to form uniform mixture.
- After that mixture is allowed to pass through sieve no. 8 and the granules were dried by using hot air oven at 50°C for 15-20 minutes.
- Then the dried granules are again allowed to pass through sieve no. 22.
- By using direct compression method herbal chewable oral care tablets were produced by punching the above dried granules with single punch machine.

EVALUATION OF HERBAL CHEWABLE ORAL CARE TABLET

F1, F2, F3 was prepared and subjected to following evaluation method.

1. Physical Evaluation:

The colour, state, and appearance of the chewable oral care tablet were examined visually.

2. Pre-compression evaluation:

Angle of repose:

The angle of repose is the maximum angle formed between the surface of a powder pile and the horizontal plane. It is used to assess the flow properties of powders, where a lower angle indicates better flow. It is calculated using:

$$\tan \theta = h / r$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Where,

θ is the angle of repose, h is the height of the pile, and r is the radius of its base.

Angle of repose as an indication of powder flow

The angle of repose or degrees	Flow
< 25	Excellent
25 – 30	Good
30 – 40	Passable
> 40	Very poor

Method:

A funnel was fixed at a constant height, and granules of the herbal chewable oral care tablet were allowed to flow freely to form a conical heap.

The height and radius of the heap were measured, and the angle of repose was calculated. Care was taken to ensure smooth and uniform flow of particles.

Bulk density:

Bulk density was defined as the ratio of the mass of powder to its bulk volume. A known quantity of powder was introduced into a 100 mL graduated cylinder. The cylinder was dropped three times from a height of 1 inch at 2-second intervals, and the initial volume was recorded. Bulk density was calculated using:

$$\text{Bulk density} = \text{mass} / \text{bulk volume}$$

Tap density:

Tap density was defined as the ratio of the mass of powder to its tapped volume. The same cylinder was tapped 100 times from a height of 1 inch at 2-second interval and the final volume was recorded. Tap density was calculated using:

$$\text{Tap density} = \text{mass} / \text{tap volume}$$

Hausner's Ratio:

Hausner's ratio is an indirect measure of powder flowability calculated using bulk and tapped densities. It was determined using the formula:

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \text{Tapped density} / \text{Bulk density}$$

Lower values indicate better flow properties.

Carr's Index:

Carr's index (compressibility index) is used to evaluate powder flow based on bulk and tapped densities. It was calculated using:

$$\% \text{ Compressibility} = ((\text{tap density} - \text{bulk density}) / \text{tap density}) \times 100$$

Flow properties were interpreted using standard compressibility index ranges.

Carr's index as an indication of powder flow

Compressibility index	Flow
5 – 15	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair to passable
23 – 35	Poor
33 – 38	Very poor
> 40	Very very poor

3. Post compression evaluation:

a) Weight variation:

Twenty tablets were individually weighed and the average weight was calculated. Individual weights were compared with the mean weight to ensure uniformity as per Indian Pharmacopoeia (IP) limits.

Weight variation specification as per I.P

Average weight (mg)	Maximum % difference
130 or less	10%
130 – 324	7.5%
> 324	5%

b) Hardness:

Tablet hardness was evaluated using a Monsanto hardness tester. Ten tablets from each formulation were tested, and the force required to fracture each tablet was recorded.

c) Friability:

Friability was determined using a Roche friabilator. Twenty pre-weighed tablets were rotated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes. Tablets were dedusted and reweighed, and friability was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ friability} = ((\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}) / \text{initial weight}) \times 100$$

d) pH:

The pH was measured using a calibrated pH meter. Tablets were dissolved in 200 mL of distilled water in separate beakers, and the pH of each solution was recorded.

e) Disintegration time:

Disintegration test was performed to determine the time required for tablets to break into smaller particles. Six tablets (three with discs and three without) were tested using a standard disintegration apparatus in distilled water at room temperature. The average disintegration time was found to be approximately 2 minutes.

FORMULATION OF HERBAL TOOTH POWDER

SR. NO	INGREDIENTS	F1	F2	F3
1	<i>Salvadora persica</i> powder	3g	3g	3g
2	Sodium bentonite clay	4.5g	5g	6g
3	Himalayan rock salt	3g	3g	3g

4	Calcium carbonate	6g	6.5g	8g
5	Menthol crystals	0.2g	0.2g	0.2g
6	Xylitol	2g	2.5g	3g
7	Silica	3.8g	3.8g	3.8g

Procedure:

- Sift all powders (*Salvadora persica*, Sodium bentonite clay, Calcium carbonate, Silica, Himalayan rock salt, Xylitol) through an 80 mesh sieve to remove lumps and ensure uniform particle size.
- Crush menthol crystals in a mortar to a fine powder and sieve if necessary for uniformity.
- In a clean mixing container, combine all sifted powders.
- Mix thoroughly for 5-10 minutes to ensure homogeneity.
- Pass the final mixture through the 80 mesh sieve again to achieve smooth texture.
- Transfer powder into airtight containers.

EVALUATION OF HERBAL TOOTH POWDER

F1, F2, F3 was prepared and subjected to following evaluation method.

1. Physical Evaluation:

The colour, state, and appearance of the powder were examined visually.

2. pH Determination:

About 5 g of the herbal tooth powder was dispersed in freshly boiled and cooled distilled water. The suspension was stirred thoroughly, and the pH was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter at room temperature.

3. Bulk Density:

Approximately 5 g of powder was accurately weighed and transferred into a dry 10 ml graduated measuring cylinder. The initial volume occupied by the powder was noted, and bulk density was calculated using the formula:

$$D = M / V$$

D= Bulk density, M= Mass of particles, V = Total volume occupied

4. Tapped Density:

The same sample was subjected to mechanical tapping until no further change in volume was observed. The final tapped volume was recorded, and tapped density was calculated as:

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{\text{Weight of powder (g)}}{\text{Tapped density (ml)}}$$

Angle of Repose:

The flow properties of the powder were determined by the funnel method. Approximately 25 g of powder was allowed to flow through a funnel fixed at a known height to form a conical heap. The height (h) and radius (r) of the heap were measured, and the angle of repose (θ) was calculated using:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Where,

h – height of the powder cone

r – radius of the powder cone

Angle of repose	Flow
25	Excellent
25-35	Good
35-40	Passable
> 40	Very poor

5. Foaming power:

Foaming ability was evaluated by dispersing 2 g of powder in 50 ml of water in a measuring cylinder. The mixture was shaken ten times, and the increase in volume due to foam formation was recorded. Foaming power was calculated as:

$$\text{Foaming power} = V1 - V2$$

Where,

V1 = final volume (ml), V2 = initial volume (ml).

6. Spreadability Test:

Figure:2

Physico-chemical parameters

The following were the physico-chemical parameters evaluated,

SR. NO	Parameters (%w/w)	<i>Salvadora persica</i>
1	Total ash	6.6 ± 0.12 %
2	Acid insoluble ash	2.9 ± 0.05 %
3	Water soluble ash	3.4 ± 0.10 %
4	Water soluble extractive value	20.2 ± 0.35 %
5	Alcohol soluble extractive value	29.3 ± 0.42 %
6	Moisture content	13 ± 0.20 %

About 0.6 g of powder was placed between two glass slides, and a load of 1.13 kg was applied for 30 minutes. The diameter of the spread sample was measured in centimeters and recorded as an index of spreadability.

7. Abrasiveness:

Abrasiveness was evaluated by rubbing 1 g of powder on a glass slide for 15 minutes. The surface was examined for scratches and recorded qualitatively as positive or negative, with higher scratch intensity indicating greater abrasiveness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preparation of plant extract

Extraction of *Salvadora persica* was carried out by maceration, and the obtained extract was subsequently used for phytochemical studies.

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to detect various phytochemical constituents. The preliminary phytochemical study revealed the presence and absence of certain phytochemicals in the extract of *Salvadora persica*.

SR. NO	Chemical constituents	<i>Salvadora persica</i>
1	Alkaloids	-
2	Carbohydrates	+
3	Flavonoids	-
4	Saponins	+
5	Glycosides	+
6	Tannins	-
7	Phenols	+

Invitro-Antimicrobial activity

The antimicrobial activity of the extract was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method against *Lactobacillus*. The standard amoxicillin disc (positive control) produced a zone of inhibition of 10 mm, while the test extract showed a zone of 7 mm. These findings suggest that the extract exhibits moderate antimicrobial activity compared to the standard.

Sr. No	Test samples	Zone of inhibition (mm)
1	Control	10
2	Extract	7

Antioxidant activity

The Antioxidant activity was expressed in terms of % inhibition, and the results are presented in the following table.

Concentration	Absorbance	% Inhibition
10	0.590	15.7
20	0.515	26.4
30	0.440	37.1
40	0.360	48.5
50	0.290	58.5

Formulation of Herbal Gel Toothpaste

Salvadora persica herbal gel toothpaste was prepared and transferred into an aluminum collapsible tube.

SR. NO	PARAMETERS	F1	F2	F3
1	Colour	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
2	Odour	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic

3	Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
4	pH	7.20 ± 0.01	7.45 ± 0.01	7.50 ± 0.02
5	Spreadability	2.90 ± 0.10	3.10 ± 0.10	2.50 ± 0.10
6	Abrasiveness	Slightly good	Good	Slightly good
7	Fragrance	Mildly aromatic with faint peppermint scent	Fresh, pleasant, and characteristic Odour	Strong, pungent, and medicinal odour
8	Shape retention	Moderate	Good	Poor

Formulation of Herbal Chewable Oral Care Tablet

Salvadora persica herbal chewable oral care tablet was prepared and transferred into a dry, airtight container.

SR. NO	PARAMETERS	F1	F2	F3
1	Colour	Light brown	Light brown	Light brown
2	Shape	Circular	Circular	Circular
3	State	Solid	Solid	Solid
4	Texture	Hard & Brittle	Hard & Brittle	Hard & Brittle
5	Angle of repose (°)	25.23 ± 0.11	23.21 ± 0.08	25.32 ± 0.14
6	Bulk density (g/ml)	0.45 ± 0.01	0.50 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.01
7	Tapped density (g/ml)	0.52 ± 0.02	0.56 ± 0.01	0.54 ± 0.02
8	Hausner's ratio	1.16 ± 0.02	1.12 ± 0.01	1.13 ± 0.01
9	Carr's index (%)	13.46 ± 0.15	10.71 ± 0.12	25.32 ± 0.14
10	Weight variation (mg)	504.9 ± 1.72	499.3 ± 1.45	511.9 ± 1.60
11	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	3.41 ± 0.11	4.10 ± 0.10	3.85 ± 0.10
12	Friability (%)	0.85 ± 0.01	0.65 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.01
13	pH	7.20 ± 0.03	7.40 ± 0.02	7.00 ± 0.03
14	Disintegration time	2.58 ± 0.08	1.0 ± 0.0	2.82 ± 0.08

Monsanto hardness tester

Disintegration apparatus

Friabilator

pH meter

Formulation of Herbal Tooth Powder

Salvadora persica herbal tooth powder was prepared and transferred into a suitable container

SR NO	PARAMETERS	F1	F2	F3
1	Colour	Pale beige	Pale beige	Pale beige
2	Odour	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
3	Taste	Astringent	Astringent	Astringent
4	Texture	Fine	Fine	Fine
5	Appearance	Powder	Powder	Powder
6	pH	6.80 ± 0.05	7.00 ± 0.05	7.20 ± 0.05
7	Bulk density (g/ml)	0.55 ± 0.01	0.53 ± 0.02	0.57 ± 0.01
8	Tapped density (g/ml)	0.65 ± 0.02	0.64 ± 0.03	0.68 ± 0.01
9	Angle of repose (°)	29.38 ± 0.35	30.11 ± 0.52	27.53 ± 0.38
10	Foaming power	8.00 ± 0.35	7.50 ± 0.40	9.00 ± 0.25
11	Spreadability	2.60 ± 0.10	2.90 ± 0.10	3.40 ± 0.10
12	Abrasiveness	Slightly good	Slightly good	Good

DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated the oral care potential of *Salvadora persica* through the formulation and assessment of herbal gel toothpaste, chewable oral care tablets, and tooth powder. The selection of *Salvadora persica* was based on its well-established traditional use as a natural oral hygiene agent and its reported antimicrobial and antioxidant properties.

The aqueous extract obtained by maceration revealed the presence of key phytoconstituents such as glycosides, saponins, carbohydrates, and

phenolic compounds. These bioactive components are known to contribute to oral health by inhibiting pathogenic microorganisms, preventing plaque formation, and providing antioxidant protection to oral tissues. The use of aqueous extraction supports the retention of polar compounds, enhancing the biological activity of the extract.

Among the three herbal gel toothpaste formulations, F2 exhibited superior physicochemical characteristics, including optimal pH, good spreadability, appropriate abrasiveness, and better retention on tooth surfaces. These properties are essential for

ensuring effective plaque removal and prolonged contact of active constituents with oral tissues. Similarly, the herbal chewable oral care tablet formulation F2 demonstrated acceptable weight variation, adequate hardness, low friability, and rapid disintegration, facilitating efficient release and action of the active components within the oral cavity.

In the case of herbal tooth powder formulations, F3 showed better performance with uniform particle size, good flow properties, and controlled abrasiveness. These attributes contribute to effective mechanical cleansing while minimizing potential damage to dental enamel.

The antioxidant activity of the extract, as demonstrated by the DPPH assay (58.5% inhibition), indicates its capacity to neutralize free radicals and reduce oxidative stress associated with oral diseases such as periodontitis. Furthermore, the antimicrobial activity against *Lactobacillus* species, although lower than the standard amoxicillin, confirms its potential as a natural antimicrobial agent. The comparatively moderate activity may be advantageous for long-term use by reducing the risk of antimicrobial resistance and adverse effects associated with synthetic agents.

Overall, the findings suggest that *Salvadora persica* extract can be effectively incorporated into various oral care formulations with satisfactory physicochemical and biological properties. The study supports its

traditional application and highlights its potential as a safe, natural, and effective alternative for modern oral hygiene products.

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REFERENCES

1. Haque M, Singh AK, Maurya SK, Seth A. Formulation development, physicochemical characterization and evaluation of anti-microbial activity of herbal tooth gel. *J Chem Pharm Res.* 2014;6(3):1279–1285.
2. Sabbagh HJ, AlGhamdi KS, Mujalled HT, Bagher SM. The effect of brushing with *Salvadora persica* (Miswak) sticks on salivary *Streptococcus mutans* and plaque levels in children: a clinical trial. *BMC Complement Med Ther.* 2020; 20:53. doi:10.1186/s12906-020-2847-3
3. Partha N, Snigdha P, Laxmidhar M. Formulation development and in vitro evaluation of dental gel containing ethanol extract of *Tephrosia purpurea* Linn. *Int J Pharm Pharm Sci.* 2016;8(8):132-141.
4. Abhary M, Al-Hazmi A-A. Antibacterial activity of Miswak (*Salvadora persica* L.) extracts on oral hygiene. *J. Taibah Univ. Sci.* 2016; 10:513–520. doi: 10.1016/j.jtusci.2015.09.007
5. Dwivedi S, Gupta S. Formulation and evaluation of herbal gel containing *Sesbania grandiflora* (L.) Poir. leaf extract. *Acta Chim & Pharm Indica.* 2012;2(1):54–59.
6. Al Bratty M, Makeen HA, Alhazmi HA, Syame SM, Abdalla AN, Homeida HE, Sultana S, Ahsan W, Khalid A. Phytochemical, cytotoxic, and antimicrobial evaluation of the fruits of Miswak Plant. *J Chem.* 2020; 2020:4521951. doi: 10.1155/2020/4521951
7. Gautam D, Palkar P, Maule K, Singh S. Preparation, evaluation and comparison of herbal toothpaste with marketed herbal toothpaste. *Asian Journal of Pharmacy and Technology,* 2020;10(3):165-169. doi: 10.5958/2231-5713.2020.00028.8
8. Ismail AM, Mohamed EA, Marghany MR. Preliminary phytochemical screening, plant growth inhibition and antimicrobial activity. *Journal of The Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences,* 2016;15(2):112-117. doi: 10.1016/j.jssas.2014.06.002
9. Deshmukh P, Telrandhe R. Formulation and evaluation of herbal toothpaste compared with marketed preparation. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics and Drug Analysis,* 2017;10:406-410. 16.
10. Dhage V, Chougule P. Importance of oral hygiene in oro-dental diseases: A Review Study. *International Journal of Research and Review,* 2019;6(12):69–74.
11. Zare P, Saeedi M, Akbari J, Morteza-Semnani K. A review on herbal oral care products. *Journal of Mazandaran University of Medical Sciences,* 2017;26:394-410.
12. Al-Ayed MSZ, Asaad AM, Qureshi MA, Attia HG, AlMarrani AH. Antibacterial activity of *Salvadora persica* L. (Miswak) extracts against multidrug resistant bacterial clinical isolates. *Scientific World Journal.* 2016; 2016:7083964. doi: 10.1155/2016/7083964
13. Al-Bayaty FH, Zaidi WI, Abdullah MN, Emad O, Al-Obaidi MM. Effect of *Salvadora persica* (Miswak) on alveolar bone healing after tooth extraction in rat. *Journal of International Dental and Medical Research.* 2018;11(3):770-777.
14. Patil PS, More AK, Kadam S, Vishwasrao V, Patel Y. Formulation and evaluation of oro-dispersible tablets of perindopril erbumine using natural super disintegrant. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics.* 2013;3(5):44-48.
15. Reddy GG, Naina R, Abhishek N, Nasir M, Murugesh Roopashree A., Naik G.L.M. Formulation and evaluation of triclosan chewable toothpaste tablet. *World journal of*

- pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences. 2023;12(11):1189-1204. doi:10.20959/wjpps202311-26051
16. Brahmkar DM, Jaiswal SB. *Biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics, A Treatise*. 1st edition. New Delhi: Vallabh Prakashan; 1995.
 17. Nagar N. Formulation and evaluation of floating Tablet of Isradipine. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*. 2024;30(5):9250-9259. doi: 10.53555/kuey.v30i5.4541
 18. Reddy GG, Naina R, Abhishek N, Nasir M, Murugesh Roopashree A., Naik G.L.M. Formulation and evaluation of triclosan chewable toothpaste tablet. *World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences*. 2023;12(11):1189-1204. doi:10.20959/wjpps202311-26051
 19. Brahmkar DM, Jaiswal SB. *Biopharmaceutics and pharmacokinetics, A Treatise*. 1st edition. New Delhi: Vallabh Prakashan; 1995.
 20. Marion J. Toothpaste Tablets: a new way to brush your teeth. *HowStuffWorks*. 2019 Mar 29.
 21. Arshad Z, Abrar A, Nosheen S, Mughal T. Determining cadmium levels in herbal tooth powders purchased from street markets in Lahore, Pakistan. *Kuwait Journal of Science*. 2020;47(1):1-8.
 22. Dudhe SB, Doijad CR. Formulation and evaluation of herbal toothpowder. *J Crit Rev*. 2020;7(18):5008–5028.
 23. Bharathi M, Rajalingam D, Vinothkumar S, Artheeswari R, Kanimozhi R, Kousalya V. Formulation and evaluation of herbal tooth powder for oral care. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Life Sciences*. 2020;8(1):1–5. doi:10.26452/ijprls.v8i1.1145
 24. Asnotikar G, Shetty AS, Mithun C, Nayak R, Shilpashree VK. Development, standardization and microbiological appraisal of herbal dentifrice prepared from *Achyranthes aspera* Linn. (Apamarga) leaves. *World Journal of Current Medical and Pharmaceutical Research*. 2022:131-138.
 25. Mamatha A, Swathi Vijaya P, Vinutha L, Hemalatha S. Formulation and evaluation of herbal toothpowders using Indian nettle, coconut spathe, tulsi and others. *Int J Pharm Res Appl*. 2022;7(1):416–422. doi:10.35629/7781-0701416422
 26. Dakhurkar SP, Mijgar PV, Wani SD, Murkute PM. Preparation and evaluation of herbal tooth powder. *World J Pharm Res*. 2019;8(10):944–948. doi:10.20959/wjpr201910-15624
 27. Agrawal A, Gupta A. Exploring the factors influencing the choice of oral care products: A review on personalized approach. *Int J Oral Dent Health*. 2020;6:109. doi:10.23937/2469-5734/1510109
 28. Valkenburg C, Van der Weijden FA, Slot DE. Plaque control and reduction of gingivitis: the evidence for dentifrices. *Periodontol* 2000. 2019;79(1):221–232. doi:10.1111/prd.12297
 29. Scherer W, Gultz J. The ability of an herbal mouthrinse to reduce gingival bleeding. *J Clin Dent*. 1998;9(4):97–100.
 30. Jensena JL, Barkvoll P. Clinical implications of the dry mouth: Oral Mucosal Diseases. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. 1998;842(1):156-162. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.1998.tb09643.x
 31. Ledder RG, Latimer J, Humphreys GJ, Sreenivasan PK, McBain AJ. Bacteriological effects of dentifrices with and without active ingredients of natural origin. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*. 2014;80(20):6490-6498. doi:10.1128/AEM.01611-14
 32. Ojha S. Formulation and evaluation of antibacterial herbal mouthwash against oral

- disorders. *Indo Glob. J Pharm. Sci.* 2018; 8:37-40.
33. Chidi PC, Isima PC, Ikpa C, Udumebraye RO, Ekwem OS, Obasi TO, ... Agwu CO. Antibacterial activity of chewing stick, dental powder and toothpastes sold in Umuahia, Abia State, Nigeria. *GSC Advanced Research and Reviews.* 2022;13(1):039-049. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7664635
34. Anitha A, Praveen G. Use of herbs in preventive dental care. *Journal of Education and Ethics in Dentistry,* 2015;5(2):55. doi:10.4103/0974-7761.188571
35. Al-Kholani AI. Comparison between the efficacy of herbal and conventional dentifrices on established gingivitis. *Dent Res J (Isfahan).* 2011;8(2):57–63.
36. Patidar VK, Sharma A. Design, Formulation and evaluation of amiodarone HCl co-crystal tablet. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine.* 2021;7(8):2020.
37. Sure PB, Band KS, Ingole AR, Baheti JR. Formulation and evaluation of chewable tablets of anti-asthmatic drug. *Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology.* 2022;15(1):137-142. doi:10.52711/0974-360X.2022.00022
38. Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission. *The Indian Pharmacopoeia.* Ghaziabad:Government of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare; 2014.
39. Wilkinson JB, Moore RJ. *Harry's Cosmeticology.* 7th edition. New York: Chemical Publishing; 1982. p. 608–622.

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